

Evaluation Of Bioactive Constituents of Curcuma Longa and Their Formulation By In Vitro Technique

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ABSTRACT

Investigating the effect of plant bioactive chemicals against *Rhizopus oryzae* which is causative agent in mucormycosis. drugs of different origin used for treatment but has many adverse drug reactions, current investigation to find novel agents and minimum adverse reaction makes a better treatment. the current research focuses on in vitro investigation of isolated bioactive constituents present in *Curcuma longa* ethanolic extracts as well formulations of it. Method: Bioactive constituents of *Curcuma longa* are isolated, formulated and perform in-vitro broth dilution assay against *Rhizopus oryzae*. the minimum inhibitory concentration was determined for isolated, mixture and gel formulations. Result: In vitro studies, using broth dilution assay, isolated, mixture of isolated constituents and formulation of it shows good result. it was found that minimum inhibitory concentration Curcumin I, II shows 78.125 µg/ml, Curcumin II shows 156.25 µg/ml and mixture of constituents shows 39.063 µg/ml compared to standard amphotericin B 3.906 µg/ml. also studied minimum inhibitory concentration of Gel-I, II, II shows 78.125 µg/ml compared to amphotericin B. Conclusion: The isolated curcuminoids, its mixture and gel formulations have ability to protect from fungal infection associated with mucormycosis disease. The synergistic mechanism seen when mixture of isolated compounds.

Keywords: Extracts, Isolated bioactive, Curcumin, *Rhizopus oryzae*, gel, Amphotericin B, In vitro, broth dilution assay.

INTRODUCTION

The rate of fungal disease burden is increasing day by day due to infection of various fungal agents. some of the fungal diseases are rare but often severe in terms of pathogenicity, mortality. The mucormycosis is fungal disease, caused by various forms of Mucorales and many strains are involved, few like *Rhizopus oryzae* found is major association with it. During COVID-19 treatment, many patients are depending upon various treatment approaches to alleviate its sign, symptoms, and improvement in quality of life. Many individuals have immunodeficiency or co-morbidity like diabetes, cancer is suffered more to fungal infections. The overuse of treatment approaches like corticosteroid therapy also enhances blood iron level and prone for fungal infections.^{1,2}

The recent treatment or therapy involving use of anti-fungal drugs to alleviate its sign and symptoms but

there is no radical cure from the therapy. the drugs like amphotericin B, posaconazole, itraconazole, have better ability to reduce fungal burden but has many adverse effects like nephrotoxicity, skin reaction and many more.^{3,4}

The main objective of current research is to determine minimum inhibitory concentration of isolated bioactive, mixture of it and formulation of it and checked against *Rhizopus oryzae*.

METHODS

Materials:

Curcuma Longa rhizomes, ethanolic extract prepared by using soxhlation process and used for further process.^{5,6} The Amphotericin B and microbial type culture and gene bank MTCC No. 262 for *Rhizopus oryzae* used were sourced from Sciore Research Private Ltd. Pune.

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Methods:

Microtitre Broth Dilution Method used to determine minimum inhibitory concentration against *Rhizopus oryzae*. In vitro assay performed by following steps:

Isolation of bioactive from *Curcuma longa* Ethanolic extracts:

Ethanolic extracts went to conventional column chromatography in silica gel (60-120 mesh) glass column. Mixing of isolated curcuminoids in the crude form having 5gm and silica gel quantity 8gm and loaded on to the column chromatography (column of 46 × 2 cm) and elution was carried out by using chloroform: methanol with increasing polarity. All the collected fractions were subjected to TLC silica gel (60 F254) plate using chloroform: methanol (95:5) as the developing solvent system and detected as yellow spots and similar fractions with the R_f values were pooled. at 420 nm range collected curcuminoids were analyzed by UV spectrophotometry. 7,8

In vitro activity of isolated bioactive, standard and formulations:

Test items are dissolved in 10%DMSO and prepare stock solutions of concentration 10 mg/ml and Master stock solutions used for further process. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) assay performed by broth dilution method.

A pure culture of a *Rhizopus oryzae* grown overnight, in incubator and then dilution done in growth-supporting broth. The dilution of microorganisms was adjusted to a 10⁶sporangiospores/ml concentration.

for analysis different concentrations of Test Item were tested in microtiter plate as 5000 µg/ml, 2500 µg/ml, 1250 µg/ml, 625 µg/ml, 312.5 µg/ml, 156.25 µg/ml, 78.125 µg/ml, 39.063 µg/ml, 19.531 µg/ml and 9.766 µg/ml respectively. All concentrations of tests and standard were studied in triplicate. Amphotericin B was used as a Standard with concentrations. All dilutions of the Test Item were inoculated with equal volumes of the specified microorganism. The microtiter plates were then incubated at 28°C for 24 hr. Growth inhibition of the microorganisms was confirmed by Resazurin dye. Based on this MIC value was given as the lowest concentration that inhibited the growth of microorganisms. 9-14

Formulation and development of Curcuminoids gel containing Curcuminoid bioactives:

The process starts with mixing of required amount of distilled water and Carbopol 940 and then mixed mechanically by highspeed mixer. In formed resultant mixture, sodium hydroxide 10% was added vigorously as a base. In water bath with a temperature not exceeding 50 °C, the Curcuminoids bioactive constituents in a concentration of 1, 2, and 3 g were added to prepare three formulations, Gel-I (1% w/w), Gel-II (2% w/w) and Gel-III (3% w/w), respectively. In another container Separately dissolved methyl paraben in propylene glycol and were also added to this respective gel. Volume of final gel is adjusted by enough purified water and the pH was drop wise adjusted with sodium hydroxide 10%. 15

The final weight of each gel formulation was adjusted with enough water to 100 g as shown in Table 4.1.

Table 1: Composition of Gel containing Curcuminoids bioactive

Ingredients Percentage	Gel I	Gel II	Gel III
Curcuminoid bioactive constituents (gm)	1	2	3
Carbopol 940 (gm)	3	3	3
Propylene Glycol (ml)	10	10	10
Methyl Paraben (ml)	0.3	0.3	0.3
Sodium Hydroxide 10% (ml)	q.s.n.	q.s.n.	q.s.n.
Distilled Water	q.s.p.	q.s.p.	q.s.p.

q.s.n. = quantity sufficient to neutralize gel base, q.s.p = quantity sufficient to prepare 100 grams of gel

Result and Discussion: Isolation of curcuminoids from extract:

The Thin layer chromatography performed for the isolation of curcuminoids showing three distinct

layers. Each curcuminoid molecule shows migration pattern and differ from other molecule with a high affinity for the mobile phase and the least polarity of the chemicals examined, the standard curcumin has the maximum run value of 5.6 cm and an Rf value of 0.933. The values were 5.0 cm (Rf 0.83) for Curcumin I, and 4.0 cm (Rf 0.66), and 2.5 cm (Rf 0.41), for Curcumin II and III, respectively obtained. decreasing Rf for Curcumin I to III's values show increasing polarity, which indicates a better retention on the polar stationary phase.

UV analysis of isolated curcuminoids:

Isolated curcuminoids are fractions and analysed by UV spectroscopy as seen in **Figure 1**, shows distinctive absorption peaks that reflect both their minor structural variations and structural

commonalities. The conjugated diketone system and extended π -electron system of conventional curcumin (A) are responsible for its significant absorption peak at 419 nm, which is compatible with curcumin's reported λ_{max} . The peak of curcumin I (B) at 418.5 nm closely resembles the standard, indicating that it is structurally very comparable and probably contains a significant amount of curcuminoid. Curcumin II (C) similarly shows a peak at 419 nm, which confirms that its chromophoric characteristics are quite like those of the standard. Curcumin III (D) exhibits a significantly lower λ_{max} at 418 nm, indicating a modest structural change that might be caused by variations in the degree of conjugation or substituents. Through UV analysis, the identification and purity of curcuminoids with core structural similarities to curcumin are confirmed due to the near alignment of absorption maxima across all fractions.

Fig.1. UV spectra of A: Std curcumin; B: Curcumin I (Fraction I); C: Curcumin II (Fraction II) and D: Curcumin III (Fraction III)

In vitro activity of curcuminoids, standard and formulation: In in vitro assay Microtitre plate used and labelled as C1 is Media Control and C2 is Growth

Control. Test Item Concentrations are indicated in $\mu\text{g/ml}$ with other wells.

Fig. 2 Plate layout of test sample

The antifungal effectiveness of individual curcuminoids, their mixtures, and gel formulations against *Rhizopus oryzae* is demonstrated by the MIC (Minimum Inhibitory Concentration) results shown in **Table 2**. Curcumin III shown much lesser action with a MIC of 156.25 µg/ml, whereas Curcumin I and II both demonstrated considerable antifungal activity

with MIC values of 78.125 µg/ml. Remarkably, the antifungal impact was much increased by the combination of the three curcuminoids, with a decreased MIC of 39.063 µg/ml, suggesting a synergistic interaction between the fractions is shown in figures 3,4,5,6

Amphotericin B, the conventional antifungal agent, showed the highest potency with a MIC of 3.906 µg/ml; however, the curcuminoid mixture shows promising potential as a natural antifungal alternative. The gel formulations (Gel I, II, and III), each of which corresponded to individual curcuminoids, retained the same MIC as their respective active components (78.125 µg/ml), suggesting effective incorporation without loss of bioactivity.

Table 2: Summary of MIC of all test samples

Sr. No.	Test Sample	MIC
1	Curcumin I	78.125 µg/ml
2	Curcumin II	78.125 µg/ml
3	Curcumin III	156.25 µg/ml
4	Mixture of curcumin I+II+III	39.063 µg/ml
5	Gel I	78.125 µg/ml
6	Gel II	78.125 µg/ml
7	Gel III	78.125 µg/ml
8	Amphotericin B	3.906 µg/ml

Fig. 3 Curcumin-I

Fig.5 Curcumin-III

Fig. 4 Curcumin-II

Fig.6 Mixture of Curcumin-I+II+III

Fig.7 Gel-I

Fig. 8 Gel-II

Fig. 9 Gel-III

Fig.10 Plate layout of Amphotericin B

Fig. 11 Amphotericin B

CONCLUSION:

The conclusion of above study is indicating that synergy is achieved with curcuminoids bioactive molecules compared with individual effect and same is preserved in gel formulation with good stability. further studies required to explore the molecular level of action.

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